

MITIGATION OF TRANSMISSION LINE SAG BY IMPROVING THE CONDUCTOR COMPOSITION RATIO

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ABSTRACT

Frequent power outages, voltage drop, over-current and short-circuiting in power transmission are mostly as a result of transmission line sags. Several findings and surveys have been carried out by researchers to help reduce the effects of transmission line sags. This study is conducted to mitigate the effects of transmission line sags by adjusting the conductor composition. The Aluminum conductor steel-reinforced cable (ACSR) conductor composition ratio has been calculated and improvements made to help reinforce the ACSR conductor to reduce transmission line sag. Temperature and heat factors were considered as the most causes of transmission line sag. Temperature effects and heat equations were applied to conductor performance and the analysis carried out in simulation. MATLAB/Simulink software was used for result validation and performance comparison. The results presented showed two different transmission line scenarios for different transmission line length and height above the sea level; span length at different temperatures were also considered for the 250/40 Aluminum Conductor Steel Reinforced conductors (ACSR) and the developed reinforced ACSR for performance checks. The results show that the adjustment of the composition ratios of ACSR below the AL/CU ratio of 61.2/78.3 (0.782) will mitigate transmission line sag.

Keywords: ACSR, Catenary, Heat, Reinforced ACSR, Sag

INTRODUCTION

Overhead conductors are the medium used for transmission of energy (Obi and Iloh, 2016; Iloh and Obi, 2016). These conductors are exposed to wind, heat and ice. Increase in the efficiency of power system is guaranteed if the losses are minimal. The conductor's resistive, magnetic, and capacitive properties constitute the basis for these losses. The cable needs to be built in a catenary shape to limit the capacitive effects of the overhead transmission line strength (Obi *et al.*, 2021). The conductor often snaps under excessive tension. The sag is required in transmission line for conductor suspension. The conductors are positioned between two overhead towers with precise sag estimation to protect them from excessive tension. Under the maximum operating temperature of 450 °C, sag and tension are projected for an equivalent level of supports (Barett *et al.*, 2022). Transmission line towers may fail if certain design procedure is not considered and may lead to massive damage to the power system. After a systematic review of various papers, reports and articles available on transmission lines, some authors analyzed the reasons of failure and their best preventive measures. They established that the reasons for failure of transmission lines include typhoon factors, lightning factors, overlying ice factors, filthy factors, and external damage factors. As a protection strategy, they suggested that the quality of the electrical design should be improved, lightning protection measures put in place, and there should be proper tower location and correct choice of rod (CIGRE WG, 2012; Dharmender, 2014; Kondrateva *et al.*, 2020; Lui *et al.*, 2022).

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

ACSR conductors

There are several types of conductors that are used for overhead lines. The most common is the Aluminum Conductor Steel Reinforced conductors (ACSR) (Aluminum Association, 2009). Other types of conductors are all aluminum, copper and aluminum alloy (Mamala *et al.*, 2016; Ujah *et al.*, 2022; Pranit *et al.*, 2018). The desirable properties of a conductor are that it has low resistivity and has sufficient strength to be able to carry its own weight and additional load for its entire lifetime. Copper has lower resistivity than aluminum, which makes it a good electrical conductor, but has greater density, which means that the tower constructions and the insulators have to be heavier for copper conductors. This, together with the fact that aluminum is cheaper than copper, makes aluminum the more popular choice for overhead line design. Aluminum is however a weaker material than copper and this is why the core of steel is added to the conductor, to increase its strength (Harvey, 2015; Obi *et al.*, 2021)

Sag measurement techniques

Monitoring transmission line sag in an accurate and timely manner is highly important for reliable and safe operation in smart grid networks (Esosa and Obi, 2020). Real-time data on sag readings can be extremely valuable to power network operators for capacity planning and efficient maintenance of the transmission system. The literature now in publication has put out a variety of methods for precisely measuring and estimating transmission line sag. Many of them are dependent on tracking physical characteristics like temperature, tension, vibration, or optical qualities, but some alternative methods have been created using signal processing and communication technologies (Wydra *et al.*, 2018).

Physical parameter-based Measurement

Temperature-based

Transmission line elongation results from current-driven heating and external influences (Vorsic *et al.*, 2019). Temperature measurements can be used to estimate sag because it is reliant on the transmission line's temperature. A homogeneous overhead conductor's sag and temperature have an essentially linear connection (Kopsidas *et al.*, 2022; Sterc *et al.*, 2023). A third-degree equation can be used to approximate the relationship (Miren *et al.*, 2021). There are two sorts of temperature measurement techniques: indirect and direct. In indirect methods, line current data and meteorological information are used to feed a mathematical model that calculates the line temperature. The temperature of a specific location on the transmission line can be measured directly using techniques like resistance thermometers, thermistors, and thermocouples. Some other direct monitoring methods of measuring line temperature are:

- Direct monitoring of line temperature by infrared cameras.
- Direct monitoring of line temperature by optical fibres.
- Direct monitoring of line temperature based on tension measurement and
- Direct monitoring of line temperature with phasor measurement units (PMUs).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design of the catenary effects

The sag of conductors was calculated using the most common mathematical description of a conductor, which is the cosh function (Sakala, 2016). To familiarize with the mathematical background of the problem by exploring the behavior of the catenary (Harvey *et al.*, 2021). The catenary can be expressed as:

$$y(x) = a \cdot \cosh \frac{x}{a} \quad (1)$$

Where x is a parameter and a is the distance of the lowest point of x from the horizontal and determines the scalability of the curve (how quickly the catenary opens up).

Starting parameters

Before starting to calculate the sag of conductors, it is proper to define some physical constants and parameters of the line. The most important part of the calculations is to determine the mechanical tension of the conductor which is one of the key parameters that define the sag. The conductor type should also be selected, the conductor parameters that should be considered includes elasticity of conductor, thermal elongation coefficient, maximum value of conductor's mechanical tension (IEC, 2018; Zuo *et al.*, 2022; Chen and Ding, 2023).

To define the parameters of the power line section, basically 2-dimensional data is needed which defines the horizontal and vertical distance of the towers (Rawlins, 1999).

Calculating the points of the catenary

These calculations utterly rely on the mechanical tension of the conductor. However, this mechanical tension cannot be the same value in each span (between two towers) as it loses its value proportionally to the distance. To have a more uniform value of mechanical tension there are some tension towers (strain pylons), where the conductors are strained and the value of mechanical tension can be precisely calibrated.

To solve the state equation of the catenary a number of auxiliary variables are needed like steepness, medium span length and $\sigma_{horizontal}$, which is the horizontal component of mechanical tension of the conductor (Hatibovic, 2014; Novriadi 2019). Respectively these variables can be expressed as the following:

$$Steepness = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{tw}} \frac{chord^3}{span^2} \quad (2)$$

Where N_{tw} = number of towers, span = the horizontal distance between two towers;

The medium span:

$$chord = \sqrt{span^2 + (h_{j-1} - h_j)^2} \quad (3)$$

Where $h_{j-1} - h_j$ = the height of the two end points of the catenary;

Horizontal mechanical tension:

$$\sigma_{horizontal} = \frac{span}{chord} \cdot \left(\sigma_{max} - \gamma_z \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot |h_{j-1} - h_j| + b_z \right) \quad (4)$$

Where σ_{max}, γ_z is given by standard and b_z is the mechanical load capability compensated with the maximum mechanical tension. These parameters have to be calculated for each span. After that we can calculate the mean value of the mechanical tension of the conductor, σ_k .

The auxiliary variables have been initialized and now only the state equation has to be solved to σ_k . The state equation of the catenary can be given as:

$$\frac{E_{mod} \cdot \gamma_z^2 \cdot span_m^2}{24 \cdot \sigma_k^2} - \sigma_k = \frac{E_{mod} \cdot \gamma_z^2 \cdot span_m^2}{24 \cdot \sigma_{kz}^2} - \sigma_{kz} + E_{mod} \cdot \alpha \cdot (T_{conductor} - T_z) \quad (5)$$

Where E_{mod} =modules of elasticity, $T_{conductor}$ = initial temperature of conductor, T_z =final temperature of conductor= σ_k =mechanical tension.

Now we have calculated σ_k the mechanical tension of the conductors, we can calculate the points of the catenary using the catenary calculation function (Adesina and Akinbulire, 2018). The sag of the conductors is being calculated in each span for 1000 points.

Cable improvement design

Heat balance equation

Energy losses resulting from electric currents in a conductor are dissipated in the form of heat to the surrounding atmosphere. Heat dissipation from conductors can take place in the form of conduction, convection and/or radiation. Owing to the minimal contact of the conductor with the suspension insulator (Obi and Iloh, 2016) at each support tower, losses due to conduction are negligible in comparison to losses due to convection and radiation. Under steady state condition of wind, solar radiation, velocity, temperature and electric current, the following heat balance equation (Vorsic *et al.*, 2019; Riba *et al.*, 2022) will help in determining the strength of cable (ACSR).

$$q_c + q_r = I^2 r + q_s \quad (6)$$

Where I is the conductor current (A) at 60 Hz, q_c is the convected heat loss (W per unit length of conductor), q_r is the radiated heat loss (W per unit length of the conductor), q_s is the solar heat gain (W per unit length of conductor), and r is the conductor resistance (Ohm per unit length at 60 Hz).

$$r = r_a [1 + k(t - t_a)], \quad (7)$$

Where, k is function of temperature, a constant with value $k = (0.004 \text{ at } 25^\circ\text{C})$, r_a is the known value resistance at temperature t_a and t is temperature for conductor's new resistance (Aluminum Association, 2019).

Equation 6 can be usually written in the form of current as:

$$I = [(q_c + q_r - q_s)/r]^{0.5} \quad (8)$$

Change in conductor temperature

The change in conductor temperature of ACSR conductors can be calculated as follows

$$\Delta t_c = \frac{I^2 r + q_s - q_e - q_r}{P} \Delta T, \quad (9)$$

Where $\Delta T = T_f - T_0$ and P is the heat capacity of conductor =1610.54 J/Km $^\circ$ C

Also, the new conductor temperature can be given as

$$t'_c = t_{ci} + \Delta t_c \quad (10)$$

Where t_{ci} is the initial temperature. The ACSR conductor design parameters are given in Table 1.

Table 1: 250/40 ACSR conductor design parameters

Conductor Parameters	Values
q_r radiated heat loss	0.3 J/m
q_s solar heat gain	0.4 J/m
q_c convected heat loss	0.5 J/m
r resistance at 60Hz	0.0674 Ω /km
ΔT temperature change	50 $^\circ$ C
P heat capacity of conductor	1610.54 J/Km $^\circ$ C

To calculate the temperature, change enough to cause sag on transmission lines, the following calculations can be done using the above given equations,

$$I = [(0.5 + 0.3 - 0.4)/0.0674]^{0.5} = 2.436A$$

$$\Delta t_c = \frac{2.43^2 \times 0.0674 + 0.4 - 0.5 - 0.3}{1610.54 \times 10^{-3}} \times (50 - 0) = 3.042^\circ\text{C}$$

Design of a reinforced ACSR cable

The strength of most ACSR can be improved by adjusting its composition using its change in conduction temperature Δt_c of the conventional ACSR.

By lowering the composition ratio η , aluminum (AL) tempered to copper (Cu) tempered of values 61.2 % and 78.3 % respectively, the conductor strength can be improved by using the cable sag relation,

$$S_c = \frac{P \times \Delta t_c}{\eta} \quad (11)$$

Where, S_c determines the conductor strength, and η the composition ratio

For example, consider the 250/40 ACSR of heat capacity 6650, and composition ratio $\frac{61.2}{78.3}$, the conductor strength will be given as,

$$\frac{1610.54 \times 3.042}{0.7816} = 6268.2481 \text{ J/Km}^\circ\text{C}$$

To improve the conductor, change in temperature value Δt_c , we can lower the ratio η , i.e., AL tempered from 61.2 % to 53.71 %, the new cable strength will be,

$$\frac{1610.54 \times 3.042}{0.6859} = 7142.8236 \text{ J/Km}^\circ\text{C}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation parameters

The design and simulation of the sag effect on transmission lines was carried out using MATLAB/Simulink with the help of the *spanIdx* command. Random transmission line parameters, such as tension span number, and line length, transmission line height above sea level and height differences were obtained to aid the design and also the analysis and reduction of sag effects on transmission lines. Table 2 shows the design parameters, while Table 3 shows the transmission line data.

Table 2: Transmission line simulation parameters

Parameters	Values
A	1 to 15m
X	-5 to 5m
Gamma	33.30529×10^{-3} sievert
GammaZ	58.32045×10^{-3} sievert
E_modulus	7220 pascal(pa)
Conductor manufacturing, Tz	85
Span number	14 & 15

Table 3: Transmission line data for scenario 1

Tension Span No	Span No	Length(m)	Height(m)	Height Diff(m)
14	37	392.81	541.32	3.85
14	40	511.21	510.54	13.62
14	41	500.32	521.43	12.47
14	42	512.41	530.34	15.23
14	45	505.32	456.87	23.37
15	46	532.41	476.87	5.28
15	48	523.21	476.87	6.28
15	49	500.32	487.87	2.85
16	50	529.76	541.45	3.35
16	51	561.21	489.84	0.69
17	52	348.81	512.34	2.89
17	54	456.89	411.45	10.34
17	55	537.98	356.98	16.64
18	57	561.23	487.76	16.66
18	59	518.87	433.87	36.51
18	60	321.45	567.98	40.19
19	62	378.32	434.81	17

Performance analysis of conductor types

There is need to carry out a performance analysis to be able to observe the performance of the sag effects on the conventional 250/40 ACSR and the designed reinforced ACSR cables. This analysis will help determine how cable manufacturers will be able to design sag withstanding cables using the developed specifications. The plots in Fig.s 1, 2, 3 and 4 each catenary plot of the sag effects as determined from each cable type shows the strength of the cable type and its ability to withstand heat, wind and other factors that might lead to transmission line sag.

Scenario (Span = 14)

Fig.s 1 to 4 show the comparison of sag effects on the conventional 250/40 ACSR cable and the developed reinforced ACSR cable, the comparison is been done for 5 different temperature values, 10, 70, 120, 150 and 170 ° C, from the sag plots, it can be seen that sag length is seen to increase as temperature increases. The sag length is seen to be more reduced for the developed reinforced ACSR cable than the conventional 250/40 ACSR.

Fig. 1: Sag plot at 10 °C for compared ACSR cables

The sag length in span 2 of the conventional 250/40 ACSR is more as compared to the first span, this is as a result of the low drop in sag of span causing drastic sag in the second and third sag. Fig. 1 presents the strength plot of the compared cable types.

Fig. 2: Plot showing cable sag factor against tension span at 10 °C

Fig. 3: Sag plot at 70 °C for compared ACSR cables

The sag length in span 3 of the conventional 250/40 ACSR is seen to drop to about 11m as temperature increases to about 70 °C as compared to that of 10 °C at 10.1, showing that temperature rise is a major cause of sag in transmission lines as can be seen in Fig. 3. The sag of the span 3 in the developed reinforced ACSR is only about 5.45 which is almost half of the sag in the conventional ACSR. Fig. 4 presents the strength plot of the compared cable types.

Fig. 4: Plot showing cable sag factor against tension span at 70 °C

CONCLUSION

The study has analyzed the causes of sag on transmission lines courtesy of heat and temperature. It has shown that heat as a result of temperature change is one of the main causes of overhead line sag. The result presented has compared the sag effects of 2 different conductors at different temperature for a span length of 14. The result presented also showed that improving the composition ratio Al/Cu of conductors will help improve its resistance to heat as a result of temperature change with the overhead sag being more as temperature rises and composition ratio reduced.

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